

SHORT NOTES

PREPARATION OF THORIUM JELLIES WITH PYRIDINE BASES

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For the first time Prakash and Dhar (this *Journal*, 1929, 6, 587) reported the formation of thorium molybdate, arsenate and phosphate jellies, by metathetical reactions. Subsequently Prasad (*ibid.*, 1936, 13, 128) also obtained thorium phosphate jelly by peptising thorium hydroxide with phosphoric acid, and dialysing the sol. Later on, Mushran (*Nature*, 1946, 168, 95) prepared thorium borate jelly from thorium nitrate and borax solutions. Attempts have been made to prepare thorium hydroxide jelly, but not with much success, though thorium hydroxide sol has been investigated in details. We have now been able to prepare a jelly of hydrous thorium oxide by using pyridine and 2-aminopyridine as bases.

The method of preparing this jelly consists in treating known amounts of thorium nitrate solution with varying amounts of pyridine or 2-aminopyridine, diluted with requisite amounts of water in order to keep the total amount the same in each case. The contents are shaken to get a homogeneous mixing. A clear solution is first obtained, which soon develops opalescence, and becomes viscous on standing. In case the concentrations of the constituents are favourable, firm translucent jellies are obtained. These are stable, uniform in texture and undergo a little syneresis on long standing.

The best jellies with pyridine were obtained when 5 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution (concentration being approximately 5% by weight corresponding to 22.74 g. of ThO_2 per litre) was mixed with 1.9 to 3.1 c.c. of 10% pyridine solution. The total volume kept each time was 10 c.c. In case of jelly formation with 2-aminopyridine, the best jellies were obtained when 2.9 to 3.1 c.c. of 2-aminopyridine solution (concentration being approximately 5% by weight) was used against 5 c.c. of 5% approximately thorium nitrate solutions under conditions similar to above.

It will be interesting to note that the best jellies are obtained between the p_H range 5.6 and 6, with pyridine as well as aminopyridine. But if the same p_H range is attained by using ammonia or alkali hydroxides, no jellies are formed, these reagents affording only partial gelatinous precipitates.